

A Study on Faunal Biodiversity in Wall Paintings of Jhunjhunu District

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Abstract Jhunjhunu is a district located in the shekhawati region of Rajasthan, India. It is well known for its fresco art and meticulously engraved architecture of Haveli's. It's famous for the world largest open air art gallery. Shekhawati region of Rajasthan is very rich in Wall Paintings. Most of the wall paintings of shekhawati area are in Haveli's. At the core of the tradition of making these ancient paintings is the feeling of religious beliefs, auspicious sentiments, beer worship and healthy entertainment. Wall paintings also identified and define the region and help one to understand the natural aspects like - climate, season, topography, flora and fauna. This study focuses on the diversity of animals in wall Painting of Jhunjhunu district. These frescoes are painted on havelis, cenotaphs, forts, bavari (step well) are adorned with the depiction of mythological and historical themes, spiritual animals, the daily day life scenes and at some places are depicted erotica and even imaginary. Within these broad outlines, the subjects were picked at random. Famous Havelis such as Arjun das Goenka Haveli museum, Roop Niwas Kothi, Morarka Havelis, Dr. Ramnath A Poddar Haveli museum, Ramgarh fresco Hotel, The Alsisar Mahal, Mohanlal Ishwardas Haveli, Tibrewala Hakaniram Narsingh das Haveli, Balkishan Lakhotiya Haveli, Kailash Shastri Haveli, Nemana Ki Haveli etc. exhibit Shekhawati art.

Keywords Faunal Biodiversity, Fresco Painting, Shekhawati, Jhunjhunu.

Introduction The shekhawati area of Rajasthan is well known for its hundreds of exquisite muraled havelis and for having the largest outdoor art gallery in the world. The areas comprised of multiple loans containing thousands of paintings and other decorative arts, such as havelis, temples, and stunning architecture. The beautiful havelis and their art work are credited to all the Marwari merchants who financed their success. As the shekhawati region is spread out over around 13784square kilo meter. In Nawalgarh, Mandawa, Churu, Jhunjhunu, Bissau, Mahansar, Ramgarh, Alsisar and Fatehpur. We might discover painted havelis of shekhawati which having faunal biodiversity. Biodiversity can also be seen in these wall paintings, in which pictures of different animals and birds can be seen. The mention of animals and birds in the wall paintings reflects the biodiversity found at that time. In various paintings of shekhawati, there are many animals like cow, elephant, monkeys, squirrels etc. are mentioned, and birds like peacock, pigeon, parrot etc. are also depicted.

Objective of study This study focuses on the diversity of animals in wall Painting of Jhunjhunu district. These frescoes are painted on havelis, cenotaphs, forts, bavari (step well) are adorned with the depiction of mythological and historical themes, spiritual animals, the daily day life scenes and at some places are depicted erotica and even imaginary.

Review of Literature The great majority of these paintings date from the second half of the nineteenth and the first quarter of the twentieth centuries, but there are also earlier examples. The painting looks so attractive from a distance and has created a Wave of independent publications starting with Rajasthan. The painted walls of shekhawati by F. Wacziarg and A Nath (1982) and more recently Shekhawati painted township by K. Singh (1995) and the Lavishly produced shekhawati Rajasthan painted home by P Rakes and K. Lewis (1995). Coopers new guide is painted in the same format as his earlier Rajasthan. The guide to the painted towns of shekhawati (with street maps) (Churn, no date 1987, according to

the book under review P.229), but it contains many more photographs and is more voluminous.

The presence of animals and birds in the wall paintings of Shekhawati reflects their Culture, the relationship of humans with bird and the creatures found at that time.

The diversity of animals and birds is visible in the havelis of different areas of Shekhawati. The Havelis of shekhawati have paintings on different theme which kept changing with time. Along with this, their biodiversity is also diverse. From the book 'Geography of Rajasthan ' by Lajpat Rai bhalla, we get information about the climate, geographical source, drainage, environmental minerals, natural vegetation, Public gatherings, tourism etc. of Rajasthan and Shekhawati which will be helpful in the research.

In Harfool Singh Arya's book "The overview and contribution of the destination of shekhawati" the multi-faceted historical literary culture and artists' traditions of Rajasthan have been depicted in the construction of building with Giti Chige. From this book, important information about the historical nature of shekhawati will happen.

Sanjay Bhalotia (2004) has given a spatial description of the main tourist places of shekhawati in his book "Ecological basis of tourism in shekhawati". He said that the wall paintings have a special influence in the fame of these tourist places of shekhawati. Due to the artistic beauty of motion pictures, this area has become famous. It has its unique identity not only in Rajasthan but also in entire India and the world; hence it is also useful in this study.

In the book " Shekhawati Haveli painting: A cultural introduction" R.P.S Rathore (2014) has talked about the major incarnation of lord Vishnu depicted in the early paintings of shekhawati. These wall paintings give a glimpse of the immediate geographical nature. This gives us an understanding that is gained about the chronology of geographical development. Ilay Cooper in his travelogue " Rajasthan: Exploring painted shekhawati" the folk life and culture of shekhawati has been described. They started his journey from Ramgarh shekhawati passing through various towns of shekhawati, he had talked about many aspects of socio- cultural life here. These wall paintings of shekhawati are very useful from the point of view of studying the Socio cultural aspect of geographical nature

Main Text

Study Area : Shekhawati is a semi-arid historical region located in the northeast part of Rajasthan, India. Its area is 13784 square kilo meter. It's northern Rajasthan 27⁰55' N 75⁰24' E. The temperature ranges from below 0.0⁰C (32⁰F) in winter to more than 50⁰C (122⁰F) in summer. The summer brings hot waves of air is called Loo. Annual rainfall is at around 450 to 600 mm.

India Map

Rajasthan Map

Shekhawati Map

Methodology

To study the murals of Jhunjhunu district, a trip was made to various towns of Jhunjhunu district. Through which biodiversity was ascertained. Nikon D-71 Camera and Olympus binocular (10x50) were used to collect murals of the area. To get the picture received from the camera clearly. A laptop was used, from which a suitable image was obtained.

Climate are divided into three seasons

1. Winter season- October to February
2. Summer seasons- March to June
3. Rainy season- July to September

The region was ruled by shekhawat Rajput. Shekhawati is located in North Rajasthan, comprising the districts of Jhunjhunu, Churu & Neem ka Thana part of Sikar district that lies to the west of Aravalli. In shekhawati, forces were initially introduced by shekhawat Rajput's in their forts & palaces. This region has been recognized as the 'open art gallery of Rajasthan' having the largest concentration of Fresco in the world. The tradition of building construction in the shekhawati region has been significant for its local culture. The traditional courtyard house is called the Haveli, dotting the small towns and villages of shekhawati stand out as a distinctly built form. We can found painted havelis of shekhawati in Nawalgarh, Mandawa, Churu, Jhunjhunu, Bissau, Mahansar, Malsisar, Ramgarh and Fatehpur

Result and Discussion

Table 1 Different Havelis of Jhunjhunu District

Village name	Haveli name	Geopostion	Animals name
Nawalgarh	Podar Haveli, Goenka Haveli	27 ⁰ 84' N 75 ⁰ 26' E	Monkey, Peacock, Cow, Horse, Camel, Dog, Oxe
Mukundgarh	Sarafas Haveli, Kanoria Haveli, Neemka Haveli	27 ⁰ 95' N 75 ⁰ 21' E	Monkey, Peacock, Cow, Horse, Camel, Dog, Oxe
Chudi ajitgarh	Beshawa Haveli, Nemani Haveli	27 ⁰ 97' N 75 ⁰ 18' E	Elephant, Peacock, Horse, Camel
Mandawa	Hanuman Prasad Haveli	28 ⁰ 05' N 75 ⁰ 15 E	Elephant, Peacock, Horse, Cow, Sparrow
Alsisar	Alsisar Mahal	28 ⁰ 32' N 75 ⁰ 28' E	Elephant, Peacock, Horse, Camel
Bissau	Jaidayal Kedia Haveli	11 ⁰ 51' N 15 ⁰ 34' W	Peacock, Snake, Fish
Islampur	Balkrishan Lakhotiya Haveli, Kailash Shastri Haveli	26 ⁰ 92' N 75 ⁰ 08' E	Elephant, Peacock, Horse
Jhunjhunu	Isardaas Haveli	28 ⁰ 13' N 75 ⁰ 4' E	Sparrow, Peacock,
Dundlod	Goenka Haveli, Nawalgarh Kua	27 ⁰ 90' N 75 ⁰ 21' E	Sparrow, Monkey, Peacock, Cow, Horse, Camel, Dog, Oxe

Findings